

A Study to Explore the Extent of Coagulation Profile and its Correlation with the Severity of TBISandeep Yadav¹, Madhu Priya²¹Assistant Professor, Department of General Surgery, Netaji Subhas Medical College and Hospital, Bihta, Patna, Bihar, India²Assistant Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Netaji Subhas Medical College and Hospital, Bihta, Patna, Bihar, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract**Aim:** The aim of the present study was to explore the extent of coagulation profile derangements, its correlation with the severity of TBI, and clinical outcome.**Methods:** The study was performed on patients with isolated head injury in department of General Surgery for one year. A total of 100 patients in the age group of 20 to 70 years were studied.**Results:** Majority of the patients belonged to the age group 41-50 years followed by 51-60 years. 80% were male and 20% were females in the present study. Road traffic accident was the primary (75%) mode of injury. In patients with MHI, 64% of the study population had coagulopathy while 48% of the patients with SHI were found to have coagulation abnormalities. The patients with SHI were divided into two groups. The first group included 40 patients and had GOS 1 or GOS 2. The second group included 8 patients and had GOS 5. p-Value for DIC score was < 0.001 and is statistically significant. p-Value in both PT and APTT was < 0.05 and was significant. However, it was not significant for D-dimer, fibrinogen, and platelet counts. In patients with MHI, p-value in case of DIC score, platelet count, APTT, and D-dimer was < 0.001 and was highly significant. p-Value in PT was < 0.05 and found to be statistically significant, however, it was not significant for fibrinogen.**Conclusion:** The patients of isolated head injury are at high risk of developing coagulation abnormalities. Coagulopathy is directly associated with the severity of TBI, GCS, and is independently associated with poor outcome. DIC score is a useful parameter in the prediction of prognosis of head injury patients. The timely intervention in such patients can help improve prognosis. The analysis of coagulation parameters are useful predictors of outcome and can be used to explain the relatives about prognosis and course of the patient during the hospital stay.**Keywords:** coagulopathy, TBI, DIC score, head injuryThis is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Traumatic brain injury (TBI) remains a leading cause of death and disability worldwide. [1] The initial insult often results in disruptions of the cerebral vasculature and pathological alterations of the blood-brain barrier (BBB) which may evolve into haemorrhagic lesions. In addition, TBI-associated factors may disturb the body's haemocoagulative capacity and alter the delicate balance between bleeding and thrombus formation leading to a substantial exacerbation of the initial injury sustained. [2-5]

Recent evidence suggests that the acute phase after TBI is rather characterised by dysfunction of the coagulation cascade and hyperfibrinolysis, both of which likely contribute to haemorrhagic progression. This may then be followed by platelet

dysfunction and decreased platelet count while the clinical implication of these alterations remains unclear. At later stages, a poorly defined prothrombotic state emerges, partly due to fibrinolysis shutdown and hyperactive platelets.⁶⁻⁸ Haemostatic alterations, in particular those during the acute phase after TBI, have been associated with higher mortality and more unfavourable outcome than in non-coagulopathic TBI patients. [2,4,9-11]

Coagulation abnormalities frequently occur following TBI and the incidence of the disturbance in the coagulation parameters varies considerably. [2,9] Goodnight et al [12] first recognized that tissue thromboplastin, of which brain is a rich source, is released into the circulation resulting in uncontrolled activation of clotting factors leading to depletion of

coagulation proteins, which may eventually result in disseminated intravascular coagulation characterized by systemic coagulopathy, intravascular coagulation and hemorrhage after the clotting factors are consumed. Stein et al [13] found a strong association between severity of coagulopathy and density of intravascular coagulation. This insult to hemostatic system is further aggravated by the infusion of large number of colloids, crystalloids and massive blood transfusion resulting in dilutional coagulopathy. Further, acidosis and hypothermia, which commonly follow traumatic injury, also add on to the hemostatic insult forming a vicious triad of coagulopathy, acidosis and hypothermia. Coagulopathy has a significant impact on morbidity and mortality of patients with TBI. [14] Mortality in patients with severe head injury with coagulopathy is found to be four times higher than in patients with head injury without any coagulopathy. [15]

The aim of the present study was to explore the extent of coagulation profile derangements, its correlation with the severity of TBI, and clinical outcome.

Materials and Methods

The study was performed on patients with isolated head injury at department of General Surgery in Netaji Subhas Medical College and Hospital, Bihta, Patna, Bihar, India for one year. A total of 100 patients in the age group of 20 to 70 years were studied. Patients having other associated injuries (extracranial trauma) like long bone fractures, chest injuries, and abdominal injuries were not included in the study. Those with pre-existing coagulopathy or

on anticoagulants, hypertension, diabetes, hepatic and renal dysfunction, or any other comorbidities were excluded.

All the selected patients were divided into subgroups of MHI and SHI based upon their Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS). Patients with GCS of 9 to 13 were classified as having MHI and < 8 as SHI. Investigations including complete hemogram, prothrombin time (PT), activated partial thromboplastin time (APTT), D-dimers, fibrinogen, computed tomography head, and ultra-sonography of chest and abdomen were done. The blood was collected at the triage area itself upon arrival of the patient without any delay and processed immediately.

All the blood investigations used to calculate DIC score (modified) were based on parameters as outlined by the International Society on Thrombosis and Haemostasis (ISTH) scoring system. APTT was also evaluated. The result of all the above blood investigations was graded on a score of 0 to 3 according to the range of normal values for a healthy population in the same laboratory. The sum of all the five blood investigations for a given patient was regarded as a DIC score. After calculation of the DIC score, the severity of DIC was graded.

Coagulopathy was defined as platelet counts less than 100,000 and PT > 15 seconds, APTT > 35 seconds, or a DIC score of more than 4. The outcome in each group was measured as per the Glasgow Outcome Scale (GOS).

Results

Table 1: Laboratory parameters with scoring system

Severity	Platelet count (in lacs)	PT (in seconds)	APTT (in seconds)	D-dimer (ng/mL)	Fibrinogen (g/L)	Score for laboratory parameter	DIC score
Normal	> 1.5	13.5	26–34	< 1,000	> 2	0	0–3
Mild derangement	1–1.5	13.5–15.0	> 34	1,000–2,000	< 2	1	3–6
Moderate derangement	0.6–1.0	15–18	> 39	2,000–4,000	< 1.5	2	7–10
Severe derangement	< 0.60	> 18	> 54	> 4,000	< 1	3	> 10

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Table 2: Demographic data

Gender	Male	Female	Total
Age group in years			
20-30	10	4	14
31-40	12	6	18
41-50	26	7	33
51-60	22	2	24
61-70	10	1	11
Total	80	20	100
Mode of injury			
RTA	63	12	75
Fall	16	4	20
Others	1	4	5
Total	80	20	100

Majority of the patients belonged to the age group 41-50 years followed by 51-60 years. 80% were male and 20% were females in the present study. Road traffic accident was the primary (75%) mode of injury.

Table 3: Incidence of coagulopathy in moderate head injury (MHI) and severe head injury

Incidence of coagulopathy	Normal	Coagulopathy
Moderate head injury	12	32
Severe head injury	8	48
Total	20	80

In patients with MHI, 64% of the study population had coagulopathy while 48% of the patients with SHI were found to have coagulation abnormalities.

Table 4: Comparison of mean values and SD of DIC score as well as individual laboratory tests in expired and discharged patients of the SHI group

Parameters	Expired or vegetative (Group 1)	Discharged (Group 2)	p-Value	Mean value
DIC score	6.3 ± 1.97	4.0 ± 2.44	< 0.001	5.91 ± 2.18
Platelet	1.64 ± 0.58	1.55 ± 0.31	> 0.05	1.63 ± 0.54
PT	15.25 ± 2.98	12.92 ± 1.48	< 0.05	14.87 ± 2.90
APTT	35.84 ± 6.38	28.8 ± 3.85	< 0.05	34.67 ± 6.53
Fibrinogen	0.71 ± 0.84	0.40 ± 0.284	> 0.05	0.66 ± 0.65
D-dimer	2812 ± 1351	2616 ± 1703.86	> 0.05	2779.73 ± 1375.57

The patients with SHI were divided into two groups. The first group included 40 patients and had GOS 1 or GOS 2. The second group included 8 patients and had GOS 5. p-Value for DIC score was < 0.001 and is statistically significant. p-Value in both PT and APTT was < 0.05 and was significant. However, it was not significant for D-dimer, fibrinogen, and platelet counts.

Table 5: Comparison of DIC score as well as individual laboratory tests in expired and discharged (GOS 3-5) patients of the MHI group

Parameter	Expired (Group 1)	Discharged (Group 2)	p-Value	Mean value
DIC score	8.0 ± 1.4	3.92 ± 2.33	< 0.001	4.23 ± 2.51
Platelet	0.9 ± 0.42	1.75 ± 0.328	< 0.001	1.69 ± 0.40
PT	17.05 ± 1.76	13.75 ± 2.13	< 0.05	14.01 ± 2.26
APTT	24.05 ± 4.03	34.93 ± 10.71	< 0.001	34.1 ± 10.72
Fibrinogen	0.47 ± 0.60	0.68 ± 0.66	> 0.05	0.66 ± 0.78
D-dimer	4122 ± 883.17	1829.23 ± 1385.15	< 0.001	2005.63 ± 1478.05

In patients with MHI, p-value in case of DIC score, platelet count, APTT, and D-dimer was < 0.001 and was highly significant. p-Value in PT was < 0.05 and

found to be statistically significant, however, it was not significant for fibrinogen.

Discussion

Traumatic brain injury (TBI) is a global health burden that affects people of all socioeconomic groups. It is a leading cause of mortality, morbidity, and disability in patients of trauma. Coagulopathy associated with TBI is well known for a long time; however, the exact pathophysiology is still poorly understood. [6,16] However, several reports suggest coagulation derailments following TBI occur secondary to the release of tissue factor which is the physiological initiator of local and systemic coagulation and fibrinolytic pathways. Coagulopathy following TBI is a dynamic process of hypercoagulability followed by hemorrhagic diathesis. [17-19]

Majority of the patients belonged to the age group 41-50 years followed by 51-60 years. 80% were male and 20% were females in the present study. Road traffic accident was the primary (75%) mode of injury. In patients with MHI, 64% of the study population had coagulopathy while 48% of the patients with SHI were found to have coagulation abnormalities. The factors responsible for coagulopathy in TBI patients are probably different from extracranial injury. Although isolated TBI does not have massive blood loss to induce coagulopathy, still it is commonly seen in clinical practice. [20] This suggests that TBI-induced coagulopathy follows a distinct pathogenic pathway that remains elusive. This also explains why the treatment and prevention of coagulopathy in TBI largely remains ineffective even today. [31] The coagulation abnormalities in TBI have been studied earlier; however, the majority of them have included patients who sustained extracranial trauma too. The scoring system of ISTH was reviewed. Authors also added APTT in the study, the usefulness of which has been reported by multiple studies including Bakhtiari et al [21], Yuan et al [22] also observed a significant correlation of APTT with poor outcome and mortality compared with other coagulation parameters.

The patients with SHI were divided into two groups. The first group included 40 patients and had GOS 1 or GOS 2. The second group included 8 patients and had GOS 5. p-Value for DIC score was < 0.001 and is statistically significant. p-Value in both PT and APTT was < 0.05 and was significant. However, it was not significant for D-dimer, fibrinogen, and platelet counts. In patients with MHI, p-value in case of DIC score, platelet count, APTT, and D-dimer was < 0.001 and was highly significant. p-Value in PT was < 0.05 and found to be statistically significant, however, it was not significant for fibrinogen. Sagar et al [23] also reported higher INR values in expired (2.28 ± 0.59) patients compared with the discharged group (1.33 ± 0.47). The IMPACT study (International Mission on Prognosis and Analysis of Clinical Trials) in TBI

found that prolonged PT at admission was present in 26% of patients and was associated with a 64% increase in mortality risk. [24] In the meta-analysis by Epstein et al [25] retrospective and prospective cohort studies were analyzed and an incidence of 35.2% of coagulopathy in TBI patients was found.

Conclusion

The patients of isolated head injury are at high risk of developing coagulation abnormalities. Coagulopathy is directly associated with the severity of TBI, GCS, and is independently associated with poor outcome. DIC score is a useful parameter in the prediction of prognosis of head injury patients. The timely intervention in such patients can help improve prognosis. The analysis of coagulation parameters are useful predictors of outcome and can be used to explain the relatives about prognosis and course of the patient during the hospital stay.

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